

Polymetallic complexes. Part-XCIX : Tetrameric and dimeric Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes with hexa- and tetradentate azodye ligands

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Abstract : Six tetrameric and six dimeric complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} with one hexadentate (bis-tridentate) $\text{O}=\text{N}-\text{N}=\text{O}$ donor and one tetradentate (bis-bidentate) $\text{O}=\text{N}-\text{N}=\text{O}$ donor azo dye ligands, 4,4'-bis(2'-hydroxy-3'-carboxy-5'-chlorophenylazo)-3,3'-dimethoxydiphenyl [LH_4] and 4,4'-bis(2'-hydroxynaphthylazo)-3,3'-dimethoxydiphenyl [$\text{L}'\text{H}_2$] have been synthesized and characterized by analytical, conductance, magnetic susceptibility, IR, electronic spectra, ESR, NMR and X-ray diffraction (powder pattern) data. The cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes are octahedral, copper(II) complexes are distorted-octahedral and a tetrahedral stereochemistry has been suggested to zinc(II), cadmium(II) and mercury(II) complexes.

Keywords : Polymetallic complexes, azo dye complexes.

Introduction

Azodyes have been immensely used for the preparation of broad spectrum chemotherapeutic drugs¹. Synthetic chemists have been inspired to synthesize new type of azodyes for the investigation of antibacterial, antifungal, antiseptic, herbicidal, pesticidal and anticancer properties. At present metal chelates having azodyes of aromatic and heterocyclic amines are being significantly applied² in food stuff technology and leather technology. In our laboratory we now focus our attention in the synthesis³ of multidentate (tetra-, penta-, hexa- and octadentate) azodye ligands and their polymeric metal complexes. The present work reports the synthesis of one hexadentate ligand (Fig. 1) and one tetradentate ligand (Fig. 2) and their twelve metal complexes.

Results and discussion

The metal complexes reported in Table 1 have the compositions $[\text{M}_4\text{LCl}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{12}]$, $[\text{M}'_4\text{LCl}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$, $[\text{M}_2\text{L}'\text{Cl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]$ and $[\text{M}^1_2\text{L}'\text{Cl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$, where $\text{M} = \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$, Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} ; $\text{M}^1 = \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$, Cd^{II} , Hg^{II} ; $\text{LH}_4 = \text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{Cl}_2\text{O}_8$ (Fig. 1) and $\text{L}'\text{H}_2 = \text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4$ (Fig. 2). All the complexes are amorphous in nature, have high melting points and are insoluble in common organic solvents but sparingly soluble in dimethylformamide. The non-electrolytic nature of the complexes is indicated by the low conductance values ($4.5\text{--}5.8 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$).

In the IR spectra of the ligands, broad bands are observed at 3250 cm^{-1} [LH_4] and at 3126.6 cm^{-1} [$\text{L}'\text{H}_2$] which may be assigned to intramolecular $\text{O}-\text{H}\cdots\text{N}$ hy-

[LH_4]

Fig. 1

[L'H₂]

Fig. 2

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of complexes

Compd.	Colour	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)					μ_{eff}
		Metal	C	H	N	Cl	
[LH ₄]	Red	-	54.7 (54.99)	3.1 (3.27)	8.9 (9.17)	11.5 (11.62)	-
[L'H ₂]	Red	-	73.4 (73.65)	4.5 (4.69)	9.9 (10.11)	-	-
[Co ₄ LCl ₄ (H ₂ O) ₁₂]	Orange red	19.5 (19.63)	27.7 (27.98)	3.1 (3.33)	4.4 (4.66)	17.5 (17.74)	2.8
[Co ₂ L'Cl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₆]	Reddish brown	13.6 (13.89)	47.9 (48.06)	4.1 (4.24)	6.4 (6.60)	8.2 (8.36)	5.1
[Ni ₄ LCl ₄ (H ₂ O) ₁₂]	Red	19.3 (19.54)	27.9 (28.01)	3.1 (3.33)	4.5 (4.67)	17.5 (17.76)	2.4
[Ni ₂ L'Cl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₆]	Red	13.7 (13.81)	47.8 (48.10)	4.1 (4.24)	6.4 (6.60)	8.2 (8.37)	3.1
[Cu ₄ LCl ₄ (H ₂ O) ₁₂]	Blue	20.7 (20.85)	27.4 (27.56)	3.1 (3.28)	4.3 (4.59)	17.2 (17.47)	1.4
[Cu ₂ L'Cl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₆]	Light blue	14.6 (14.81)	47.4 (47.54)	3.9 (4.19)	6.3 (6.52)	8.1 (8.27)	1.8
[Zn ₄ LCl ₄ (H ₂ O) ₄]	Violet	23.8 (24.16)	30.9 (31.04)	2.1 (2.22)	4.9 (5.17)	19.3 (19.68)	-
[Zn ₂ L'Cl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow	16.3 (16.56)	51.5 (51.66)	3.4 (3.54)	6.9 (7.09)	8.7 (8.99)	-
[Cd ₄ LCl ₄ (H ₂ O) ₄]	Light brown	35.1 (35.39)	26.2 (26.44)	1.6 (1.89)	4.2 (4.41)	16.5 (16.76)	-
[Cd ₂ L'Cl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	Brown	25.2 (25.44)	45.9 (46.16)	2.9 (3.17)	6.2 (6.34)	7.9 (8.03)	-
[Hg ₄ LCl ₄ (H ₂ O) ₄]	Brown	49.2 (49.43)	20.5 (20.70)	1.3 (1.48)	3.2 (3.45)	12.9 (13.12)	-
[Hg ₂ L'Cl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	Light red	37.6 (37.84)	38.2 (38.48)	2.5 (2.64)	4.9 (5.28)	6.6 (6.70)	-

drogen bonding. Disappearance of these bands in the metal chelates shows the bonding of the phenolic -OH groups to the metal atoms. The bands at 1504 cm⁻¹ [LH₄] and at 1475.8 cm⁻¹ [L'H₂] can be attributed to phenolic C-O vibration and in the metal complexes these bands appear

at 1465-1460.8 cm⁻¹ indicating the bonding of phenolic oxygen atoms of the ligands to the metal ions⁴. The sharp bands of the ligands at 1589 cm⁻¹ [LH₄] and at 1609.8 cm⁻¹ [L'H₂] can be attributed to $\nu_{\text{N}=\text{N}}$ vibrations and in the metal chelates these bands appear at ~1567 cm⁻¹

with the former ligand and at $\sim 1599.1 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ with the latter ligand which indicates the bonding of one of the azo nitrogen atoms to the metal atoms⁵. In the ligand [LH₄] $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO}^-)$ and $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO}^-)$ bands appear at 1665 and 1440 cm^{-1} and these bands appear in the complexes at $\sim 1655 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and at $\sim 1425 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ with a difference ($\Delta\nu$) of $\sim 230 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ supporting monodentate nature of carboxylate group⁶. In the metal complexes broad bands appear at $\sim 3391\text{--}3551.7 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ followed by sharp peak at $\sim 835\text{--}841.1 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 729\text{--}734.5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to -OH stretching, rocking and wagging vibrations respectively indicating the presence of co-ordinated water molecules in the complexes⁷. The conclusive evidence of bonding of the azo dye ligands to the metal atoms is proved by the appearance of bands at $\sim 555\text{--}517 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (M-O) and $\sim 460\text{--}455 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (M-N)⁸.

The magnetic moments for Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} complexes with the ligand L'H₂ are found to be 5.1, 3.1 and 1.8 B.M. respectively indicating octahedral configuration of the complexes. But the complexes of the same metal ions with the ligand LH₄ exhibit sub-normal magnetic moments of 2.8, 2.4 and 1.4 B.M. respectively could be attributed to the magnetic interaction due to super-exchange phenomenon of phenolic oxygen atom in a dimeric structure (M-O-M)¹³.

In the electronic spectra of Co^{II} complexes, four bands appear at 8552 (8587), 17235 (17308), 20350 (20410) and 32354 (32370) cm^{-1} , the first three bands can be assigned to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F) (\nu_1)$, $\rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F) (\nu_2)$ and $\rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P) (\nu_3)$ transition respectively and the fourth band is assigned to a CT band. The ligand field parameters like $Dq = 868.30$ (872.10) cm^{-1} , $B = 795.266$ (797.133) cm^{-1} , $\beta_{35} = 0.8190$ (0.8209) cm^{-1} , $\nu_2/\nu_1 = 2.0153$ (2.0156) and $\sigma = 22.100\%$ (21.8175%) suggest an octahedral geometry for the Co^{II} complexes¹⁰. In the electronic spectra of Ni^{II} complexes, four ligand field bands are observed at 10185 (10215), 17335 (17380), 24990 (25070) and 32740 (32784) cm^{-1} assignable to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F) (\nu_1)$, $\rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F) (\nu_2)$, $\rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P) (\nu_3)$ and CT transitions respectively in a distorted octahedral geometry. The ligand field parameters like $Dq = 1018.50$ (1021.50) cm^{-1} , $B = 784.66$ (787.0) cm^{-1} , $\beta_{35} = 0.7537$ (0.756) cm^{-1} , $\nu_2/\nu_1 = 1.7020$ (1.7014) cm^{-1} and $\sigma = 32.6787\%$ (32.275%) confirm the octahedral configuration for the complexes¹¹. The electronic spectra of Cu^{II} complexes exhibit one broad band at $\sim 13542\text{--}14485 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ with maxima at $\sim 14340 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$

transition in support of a distorted octahedral configuration for the complexes¹².

The ESR spectrum of the complex [Cu₂L'Cl₂(H₂O)₆] has been recorded at X-band at room temperature. The computation made by Piesach and Blumberg's method suggests the presence of two g values. The geometry around the Cu^{II} ions in the unit cell is tetragonal (elongated octahedral) with $g_{\perp} = 2.07788$ and $g_{\parallel} = 2.28815$. The axial symmetry parameter G is found to be 3.69 which suggests the absence of exchange interaction among magnetically equivalent ions in the unit cell. The g_{\parallel} is a function for representing covalency. The g_{\perp} value is found to be less than 2.3, indicating covalent nature of the complex. The trend observed for the complex $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > g_e$ (2.0023) indicates that the unpaired electron is localized in $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital¹³.

The ¹H NMR spectrum of the ligands LH₄ and L'H₂ were recorded in CDCl₃. The complex pattern observed at δ 6.924–7.811 [LH₄] and δ 7.0033–7.8864 [L'H₂] correspond to 10 and 12 phenyl protons respectively. The sharp peak observed at δ 3.835 [LH₄] and at δ 3.91 [L'H₂] correspond to six methoxy protons on each ligand¹⁴.

Table 2. X-Ray diffraction data of complexes

Compd.	Unit cell parameters	Density (g/cc)	n	Probable geometry
[Co ₄ LCl ₄ (H ₂ O) ₁₂]	$a = 5.247 \text{ \AA}$ $b = 18.617 \text{ \AA}$ $c = 5.649 \text{ \AA}$ $\alpha = 90.0^\circ$ $\beta = 91.512^\circ$ $\gamma = 90.0^\circ$ $V = 3705.59 \text{ cc}$	1.076	2	Monoclinic
[Ni ₄ LCl ₄ (H ₂ O) ₁₂]	$a = 14.880 \text{ \AA}$ $b = 18.618 \text{ \AA}$ $c = 11.827 \text{ \AA}$ $\alpha = 97.648^\circ$ $\beta = 94.634^\circ$ $\gamma = 72.195^\circ$ $V = 3089.02 \text{ cc}$	0.967	1.5	Triclinic
[Ni ₂ L'Cl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₆]	$a = 14.904 \text{ \AA}$ $b = 27.153 \text{ \AA}$ $c = 14.078 \text{ \AA}$ $\alpha = 90.0^\circ$ $\beta = 90.0^\circ$ $\gamma = 90.0^\circ$ $V = 5696.14 \text{ cc}$	0.961	4.0	Tetragonal

Graph 1. XRD graph for $[\text{Co}_4\text{LCl}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{12}]$ complex.

Graph 2. XRD graph for $[\text{Ni}_4\text{LCl}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{12}]$ complex.

Graph 3. XRD graph for $[\text{Ni}_2\text{L}'\text{Cl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]$ complex.

The XRD studies of the complexes were made with the help of X-ray diffractometer by powder pattern method and the unit cell parameter were calculated by a computer from the 2θ values (Graphs 1, 2 and 3), The direct constants of these lattices like a , b , c , α , β , γ and V (volume) shown in Table 2, suggest the probable geometry of the complexes to be monoclinic, triclinic and tetragonal respectively. The densities of the complexes were determined by the floatation method in a saturated solution of KBr, NaCl and benzene separately. The number of formula units per unit cell (n) is calculated from the relation $n = dNV/M$, where d = density of the compound, N = Avogadro's number, V = volume of the unit cell, M = molecular weight of the complex. The value of n is found to be 2, 1.5 and 4 for the above three complexes respectively which agrees well with the suggested structure of the complexes¹⁵.

The Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes are found to be four coordinated having tetrahedral geometry based upon analytical conductance and IR spectral data. The former ligand behaves as a bis-tridentate (hexadentate) ligand and forms tetrameric complexes with phenolic bridge whereas the latter ligand behave as a bis-bidentate (tetradentate) ligand forming dimeric complexes.

Experimental

All the chemicals were from BDH or SRL. The metal, carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen and chlorine were estimated by standard methods. The magnetic susceptibility measurements were made at RT by Gouy method. Conductivity measurements of the complexes were made using Toshniwal CL 01-06 conductivity bridge. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded using IFS 66U spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (10^{-2} in DMF) using Hilger-watt uvispeck spectrophotometer, ESR spectrum of the copper(II) complex on an E₄-spectrometer and NMR spectra on a Jeol GSX 400 with CDCl₃ as solvent and TMS as internal standard and X-ray diffraction (powder pattern) of the three complexes were recorded on a Phillips PW 1130 diffractometer.

Preparation of the ligands :

The azo dye ligands were prepared by the coupling reaction of the diazonium chlorides obtained from *o*-dianisidine (0.01 mol, 2.443 g) with alkaline solution of 5-chlorosalicylic acid (0.02 mol, 3.450 g) LH₄ and β -

naphthol (0.02 mol, 2.88 g) [L'H₂] at 0–5 °C.

Preparation of the complexes :

The metal chlorides in ethanol were mixed separately with ethanolic solution of the ligand [LH₄] in 4 : 1 and the ligand [L'H₂] in 2 : 1 molar ratio and the resulting solutions were heated to ~60 °C for about an hour on a heating mantle. The solutions were then cooled to room temperature and pH was maintained to ~7 by adding conc. ammonia drop by drop with stirring. The solid complex compounds formed were then washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried *in vacuo*.

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References

1. L. S. Goodman and A. Gilman, "The Pharmacological Basis of Therapeutics", 4th ed., McMillan, New York, 1970, 111; K. N. Gaint and J. K. Khanna, *Indian J. Pharm.*, 1964, **26**, 34; S. K. Gulati and K. N. Gaint, *Indian J. Pharm.*, 1966, **28**, 272.
2. A. Butulia, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1970, 1339.
3. B. B. Mahapatra and D. K. Das, *Acta Chim. Hungarica*, 1987, **124**, 387; B. B. Mahapatra, D. K. Das, D. Panda, C. D. Rao and A. L. Dutta, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1987, **26**, 66; B. B. Mahapatra and D. K. Das, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1988, **18**, 965; B. B. Mahapatra, B. K. Patel and K. C. Satpathy, *Acta Chim. Hungarica*, 1989, **126**, 207; B. B. Mahapatra and S. K. Kar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1991, **68**, 542; B. B. Mahapatra, A. K. Behera and P. K. Bhoi, *Asian J. Chem.*, 1992, **4**, 873; B. B. Mahapatra and S. K. Saraf, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2003, **80**, 696; 2004, **81**, 954; B. B. Mahapatra and Ashish K. Sarangi, *J. T. R. Chem.*, 2007, **14**, 49; B. B. Mahapatra and N. Patel, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **86**, 518; B. B. Mahapatra and A. K. Sarangi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **86**, 559.
4. L. K. Mishra and B. K. Keshari, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1981, **28**, 883.
5. R. B. King, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, **5**, 300.
6. G. B. Decan and R. J. Phillips, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1980, **33**, 227; L. J. Bellamy, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecule", 3rd ed., Chapman and Hall, London, 1975.
7. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Co-ordination Compounds", Wiley Interscience, New York, 1963.
8. J. R. Ferraro, "Low Frequency Vibration of Inorganic and Co-ordination Compound", Plenum Press, New York, 1971.

9. F. A. Cotton and P. G. Wilkinson, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", 3rd ed., Wiley Eastern, New Delhi, 1985.
10. A. B. P. Lever, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1967, 2041; R. C. Carlin, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1968, 1, 3; R. G. Devota, G. Ponticelli and C. Preti, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1957, 37, 1633.
11. L. J. Sacconi, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1968, 48, 73; A. B. P. Lever, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1968, 3, 119; C. R. Hare and C. J. Ballhausen, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1984, 40, 788.
12. S. Yamada, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1966, 1, 415; I. M. Proctor, B. J. Halthway and S. P. Nichol, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1968, 1678; C. K. Jorgensen, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1966, 10, 887.
13. F. K. Kneubuhl, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1960, 33, 1074; D. Kivelson and R. Nieman, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1961, 35, 149.
14. D. H. Williams and I. Fleming, "Spectroscopic Method in Organic Chemistry", 4th ed., Tata McGraw Hill, 1994.
15. B. R. Puri, L. R. Sharma and K. L. Kalia, "Principle of Inorganic Chemistry", S. Lal Nagin Chand and Co., 1993, p. 290.